

Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrates-A Review

By

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Abstract: Effective implementation of microencapsulation technique and cyclodextrin for the production of cosmetic textiles can be introduced as a technical textiles-based product. α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin can be applied for the aromatherapeutic textile as host molecule, because it exhibits qualities of controlled release which may be beneficial for the improvement of human life style. Cyclodextrin molecules are capable of forming inclusion compounds with fragrances that fit into the cone-shaped hydrophobic cavity. As a result, the release-fragrance rates are greatly decreased. There are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on cyclodextrin. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles. Focusing on the field of cosmetic textiles, the major interest in microencapsulation is currently in the application of attractive fragrances, vitamins, essential oils, skin moisturizing agents, skin cooling agents etc.

Keywords: Cyclodextrin (CD), Aroma Finishing, Microencapsulation, Inclusion complexes, Cotton Fabric

Introduction:

In recent years, textile materials have been found in applications in the cosmetics field. A new sector of

cosmetic textiles is introduced and several commercial cosmetic textile products are currently available in the market. On contact with human body and skin, cosmetic textiles are designed to transfer an active substance for cosmetic purposes. The principle is achieved by simply imparting the cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredients into the fabric of clothing so that with the natural movement of the body, the skin is slowly freshened and revitalized. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles.

Aroma finishing as cosmetic textiles have become very attractive innovations resulting from technological advancements represent the best strategy for success in the increasingly competitive textile industry. Fragrance finishing of textile materials has been greatly expanded and used in recent years. Fragrance finishing can be done effectively using exhaust method than any other methods. Recently, fragrances have become available that can be readily formulated into fabrics. Properly designed textiles containing effective, long-lasting fragrances would provide a significant contribution to the textile industry. The proposed research will investigate new fragrance technologies. The fragrance finished fabrics can be used in home textile applications such as wall hangings, table covers, carpets and sofa covers.

Fragrance finishing of textiles is one of the processes which enhance the value of the product by adding various odours to it. The world marketplace is constantly changing and so the demand of consumers is also increased. Everyone

desires for continuous change .i.e. something different and unique. This increase in demand, as well as tremendous competition in the market, opens up opportunities for value addition to all forms of textile materials[1]. The effective change has to be implemented in the market. By this extensive analysis, fragrance finishing is considered as emerging area and which has tumble-down the textile industry with lively value added finish by incorporating different fragrances into fabrics, leading to the production of fragranced fabrics[2]. This proved a good way to meet important emotional and emotional needs, as well as those of a pure and sensorial nature.

The human sense of smell registers not only the quality of different odours but also combines it automatic and often unconsciously with feelings ranging from agreeable to unpleasant. This connection is used in many ways. Perfumed people and merchandise become more attractive and stink bombs are used to the opposite effect. Textiles have a very large specific surface (for example 0.1 to 1 m² g⁻¹). Therefore they attract, adsorb and store various gaseous or volatile substances from their surroundings. This high adsorption capacity can become a problem with unpleasant smelling substances under desorption conditions. Desorption is accelerated by temperature, time and the possibility of gaseous exchange, for example airing. Structure of Dextrin and Cyclodextrin:

The investigation ⁽¹⁾ of US retail sales of home fragrance shows that sales increased 9.7 percent, from \$1.35 billion in 1995 to \$1.96 billion in 1999, and are projected to increase by 7.9 percent to \$2.87 billion in 2004. Pleasure and enjoyment⁽²⁾ on the one hand, is about daring to be different, but also about forgetting stress. Excitement and active wear are a form of communication. ⁽³⁾ The scents of lavender, rose, citrus or vanilla were encapsulated into fabrics, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature aromatherapy was coined in the late 1920s by the French cosmetic chemist R.M. Gattefosse,

who noticed the excellent antiseptic properties and skin permeability of essential oils

Dr. Charles Tomasino⁴ reviewed that natural starches are not very soluble in cold water. Cooking is necessary to get the starch granules to form a homogenous solution. Typically the starch granules are stirred in cold water and kept suspended by high speed mixing. As the temperature is raised, water penetrates through the amylopectin membrane solubilizing amylose. The granules swell as more and more water diffuses in enlarging to many times their original dimensions. The viscosity of the solution increases as the granules swell, reaching a maximum at the point where the swollen granules are crowding against each other. Prolonged heating and mechanical shearing cause the swollen granule membrane to rupture allowing the solubilized amylose to spill into the bulk of the solution. At this point the viscosity begins to fall off, finds a stabilized level and remains there. The starch solution can be considered as solubilized amylose molecules intermingled with ruptured swollen fragments of the amylopectin membrane. Dextrin is made by heating dry starch with a mineral acid. White dextrin is made by heating at moderate temperatures and yellow dextrin is made by heating at higher temperatures with less acid. The degree of hydrolysis is higher than for thin boiling starch so dextrin solutions have lower viscosities.

Figure-1: Structure of Dextrin⁽⁵⁾

Cyclodextrin: David Rowe reviewed that Corn is the raw material that provides the starch for cyclodextrin production

Figure-2: Microencapsulation of α -cyclodextrin, β -cyclodextrin, γ -cyclodextrin

M. Sundrarajan and Rukmani reviewed⁴ that Cyclodextrins are a group of structurally related natural products formed during bacterial digestion of cellulose. These cyclic oligosaccharides consist of (α -1,4)-linked α -D-glucopyranose units and contain a somewhat lipophilic central cavity and a hydrophilic outer surface. Due to the chair conformation of the glucopyranose units, the cyclodextrins are shaped like a truncated cone rather than perfect cylinders. The hydroxyl functions are orientated to the cone exterior with the primary hydroxyl groups of the sugar residues at the narrow edge of the cone and the secondary hydroxyl groups at the wide edge.

The central cavity is lined by the skeletal carbons and ethereal oxygens of the glucose residues, which gives it a lipophilic character. The polarity of the cavity has been estimated to be similar to that of an aqueous ethanolic solution. The natural α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin consist of six, seven, and eight glucopyranose units, respectively. The natural cyclodextrins, in particular β -cyclodextrin, are of limited aqueous solubility meaning that complexes resulting from interaction of lipophiles with these cyclodextrin can be of limited solubility resulting in precipitation of solid cyclodextrin complexes from water and other aqueous systems. In fact, the aqueous solubility of the natural cyclodextrins is much lower than that of comparable acyclic saccharides. This is thought to be due to relatively strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the crystal state. Substitution of any of the hydrogen bond forming hydroxyl groups, even by lipophilic methoxy functions, results in dramatic improvement

in their aqueous solubility. Cyclodextrin derivatives of pharmaceutical interest include the hydroxypropyl derivatives of β - and γ -cyclodextrin, the randomly methylated β -cyclodextrin, sulfobutylether β -cyclodextrin, and the so-called branched cyclodextrins such as glucosyl- β -cyclodextrin.

The general features of β -cyclodextrin⁽⁷⁾ and their applications in the textile industry have been reviewed. The use of β -cyclodextrin in the textile industry is great significance due to its wide range of application. One of the key aspects is the attachment technique of β -cyclodextrin to the textile's surface. This review deals with this in depth. Some quantification and characterization methods of Textile- β -cyclodextrin are discussed. In the last few years, the new direction in textile research is the functionalization of textile systems. It is believed that β -cyclodextrin will play a very important role in these new developments. β -cyclodextrin can act as a host for various guest molecules. This enables the development of fabrics that release chemical compounds such as fragrances and antimicrobial agents. It is concluded that there are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on β -cyclodextrin.

⁽⁵⁾ **Table-01: physical properties of Alfa CD, Beta CD, Gama CD, Lamda CD**

Physicochemical properties	Alfa CD	Beta CD	Gama CD	Lamda CD
No of glycopyranose units	6	7	8	9
Central cavity diameter	4.7-5.3	6.0-6.5	7.5-8.3	10.3-11.2
Water solubility at 25°C	14.5	1.85	23.2	8.19
Molecular weight	972	1135	1297	1459

Devinderkaur and Neelam Grewal⁽⁶⁾ reviewed that the cyclodextrin capacity to form inclusion

complexes is known for a long time, this property being used in textile industry to obtain products with applications in increasing wear comfort and realization of medical textiles.

Figure-03: Structure of α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin
 Cyclodextrins⁽⁸⁾ clamped on cellulose do not affect the cellulose's properties, and cyclodextrins keep their ability to form inclusion complex with other suitable molecules. J. Kotch⁽⁹⁾ reviewed that Complexed with cyclodextrin, perfumes are stable. B. Martel and et.al⁽¹⁰⁾ reviewed that Permanent fixation of cyclodextrins onto textiles occurred either through reaction of the functional groups of the fibre (covalent bonding), or through the formation of a crosslinked polymer that is tangled up in the fibres (noncovalent bonding)

Figure-4: Fiber-cyclodextrin binding types: a) Triazinylchloride is reacted with cyclodextrin. The product has reacted with the fiber. b) Polycarboxylic acid reacts with the fiber. The formed ester is converted to a cyclic anhydride, which is then reacted with cyclodextrin. c) The cyclodextrin and epichlorohydrin reacts with strong alkali treated cellulose.

Figure-02: Different sources of perfumed oil can be applied on cotton textiles with cyclodextrin:

Perfumed oils are found in:

flowers	cloves, hyacinth, mimosa, jasmine, orange blossom, roses, reseda, heliotrope
petals and leaves	lavender, rosemary, peppermint
leaves and stems	geranium, cinnamon, patchouli
bark	cinnamon
roots	angelica, sassafras, vetiver
tubers	ginger, iris
fruits	bergamot, lemon, lime, orange
seeds	bitter almonds, anise, nutmeg
resin	myrrh, Peru balsam, styrax

J.-P. Moldenhauer⁽¹¹⁾ and other researcher found that β -cyclodextrin is a reactive cyclodextrin derivative that can be covalently fixed to nucleophilic substrates by a substitution reaction carried out by the usual finishing procedure. This new type of surface modification means a permanent transfer of cyclodextrin properties to the treated materials. Both alkaline and acidic methods⁽¹²⁾ for MCT- β -cyclodextrin finishes have been developed to suit customers. Particularly interesting is the treatment with fragrances and antimicrobial and pharmaceutical preparations, which can be released continuously over a long period on exposure to moisture. Underwear, gloves, socks⁽¹³⁾ can be loaded with the necessary antifungal, antihistaminic, and antiinflammatory agents. Curtains with cyclodextrins can be used to improve the air in rooms or offices with smokers.

Aroma/Scent/Fragrance aesthetics:⁽¹⁴⁾

When notice a smell, sensory organs unlock in you a subjective dimension, a memory, perhaps, or a feeling – a sensory experience inside the body. This doesn't happen if only looking at something. If we consider smell a roast turkey, for example,

rather than just see it, all your memories of roast turkeys are activated – an instantaneous accessing of relevant information and memory. Smells can

Aroma Category	Aroma Compound / Aroma Chemical
Citrus: Lemon Orange	Citral, Citronellal Mandarin Oil, Decyl acetate
Floral: Carnation Gardenia Geranium Lilac Lily Rose Violet	Phenethyl salicylate Nonyl acetate Citronellal Anisyl acetate Hydroxy citronellal Rose absolute Costus oil, Methyl-2-nonenolate
Fruity: Apple Apricot Banana Grape Peach Strawberry	Benzyl acetate Allyl butyrate Amyl acetate Isobutyl isobutyrate Allyl butyrate Benzyl benzoate
Herbaceous: Clove Minty	Eugenyl acetate l-carveol, l-carvone, l-menthol
Sweet: Anise Cinnamon Honey Sweet Vanilla	Ethyl acetate, methyl sorbate Cinnamonaldehyde Allylphenoxyacetate Acetanisole Anisyl acetate

Ingredients of perfume (14,15,16): Sources of natural essential oils for perfumes (from Encyclopaedia Britannica).

thus both create a sense of anticipation and a memory of the past – and gaining access to hidden or forgotten parts of our own history is a gift indeed. It is not yet known exactly how the sense of smell works. It might be the size, shape, spin, wave length or vibration of particular molecules matching or interlocking with special receptors in the nose that cause us to react or recognize a smell. Only a few molecules are necessary for us to experience or identify scents, and characteristically, the worse a smell is, the less it takes to notice it.

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Sources of natural essential oils for perfumes (from Encyclopaedia Britannica).

Assessment of the Highest Aroma Effect of Herbal Extracts :

Extraction from the Herb

↓

Fresh flowers

↓

Boil the water

↓

Add the flowers (still it separates the Essence)

Aroma or fragrance is a chemical compound that has a pleasant smell or odor. According to research of World health organization, human stress is a problem that reduces quality of life for a large proportion of world's citizens & scientifically it was proved fragrance reduces stress has both long term and short term health benefit.

Table-03: Different sedative effects/or emotion of essential oils:

Emotion	Essential Oils with the Sedative Effects
Anxiety	Benzoin, Lemon, Chamomile. Rose, Cardamom, Clove, Jasmine
Lament	Rose
Stimulation	Camphor, Balm oil
Anger	Chamomile, Balm oil. Rose, Ylangylang
Wretchedness	Basil, Cypress, Mint, Patchouli
Allergy	Chamomile, Jasmine, Balm oil
Distrustfulness	Lavender
Tension	Camphor, Cypress, Vanilla. Jasmine. Balm oil. Lavender, Sandalwood
Melancholy	Basil, Lemon, Chamomile, Vanilla, Jasmine, Lavender, Mint, Rose
Hysteria	Chamomile, Balm oil, Lavender, Jasmine
Mania	Basil, Jasmine, Pine
Irritability	Chamomile, Camphor, Cypress, Lavender
Desolation	Jasmine, Pine, Patchouli, Rosemary

Beta cyclodextrin⁽¹⁶⁾ for fragrance finishing:

1. Successful medical application
2. It has cone shaped hydrophobic cavity which released fragrance rates are greatly decreased.
3. Finishing with cyclodextrin on cotton textiles.
4. Fragrance was capsulated with beta cyclodextrin and perfume retention onto the fabric after number of washing and exposure to sunlight.

Successful fixation technique of cyclodextrin¹⁵ like Crosslinking, Grafting, Reactive fixation, Disperse dyeing method, Electrospinning, Sol gel process, Enzymatic coupling, Polymer extrusion&Fragrance release property etc.

Finishing with microencapsulation:

The fragrance compound⁽¹⁷⁾ and the essential oil are volatile substances. The most difficult task in preparing the aromatherapy textile is how to prolong its lifetime of odours. Micro-encapsulation is an effective technique to solve this. Micro encapsulation technology¹⁸ has its vast application in various fields including textile wet processing. It is a technology, in which very small particles of liquids, solids and gases are trapped within a very thin coating of polymeric material(s). For textile wet processing applications core materials includes dyes, pigments, essential oils, vitamins, anti bacterial agents, anti UV agents etc. The microcapsules obtained in slurry or free flowing powder form is applied to fabric to achieve various effects. In today's life customer needs differ from that of conventional needs, where micro encapsulation technology plays a significant role to meet today's market demand by providing multiple advantage using one single product. So textile is a product, which can easily fulfill for fashion and also protection at the same time.

Micro encapsulation has different purposes like

- Protection of enclosed material and improved storage life
- Conversion of liquid component to dry solid system
- Ensuring separation of incompatible components
- Odour masking
- Dust and pH control
- Controlled diffusion of active components, through the shell wall
- Change of weight or volume

Mechanism of microencapsulation (19):

Figure-05: Mechanism of microencapsulation

Many different manufacturing approaches have been adopted for microencapsulation. The most commonly used microencapsulation processes⁽²⁰⁾, including Complex Coacervation, Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility, Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation, Spray Drying, Centrifugal Extrusion, Air Suspension Coating, Pan Coating, and Emulsion Hardening Process

Important testing of cyclodextrin and cosmetic textiles⁽²¹⁾:

1. **SEM (Scanning electron microscopy):** is used to study the microscopic aspect of the raw material (cyclodextrin and guest

substances respectively) and the product obtained by co-precipitation/evaporation.

2. **Infra-Red (IR) Spectroscopy:** is used to estimate the interaction between cyclodextrin and guest molecules in the solid state
3. **Thin Layer chromatography (TLC):** helps to identify the complex formation between guest and host molecule.
4. **X-ray diffractometry:** to detect inclusion complexation in the solid state.
5. **Single crystal X-ray structure analysis:** to determine the detailed inclusion structure and mode of interaction
6. **Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR):** to determine the cyclodextrin cavity in solution as well as direction of penetration of guest molecules into the cyclodextrin cavity.
7. **Olfactometry:** to know the intensity of fragrance

Successful example of using cyclodextrin for aroma finishing⁽²²⁾ :

Sensorial evaluation of scent intensity with cyclodextrin

Fragrance	Scent intensity					
	5 days	10 days	15 days	20 days	25 days	30 days
Rosemary	++ ++ +	+++++	++++	+++	+++	++
Lavender	++ ++ +	++++	+++	++	++	+
Jasmine	++ ++ +	+++++	++++	+++	++	++
Lemon	++ ++ +	++++	+++	++	+	+
Sandalwood	++ ++	+++++	++++	+++	+++	++

	+					
--	---	--	--	--	--	--

+++++ express very strong, ++++ express strong, +++ express common, ++ express weak, + express very weak.

Safety and pre-caution of Cyclodextrin for Aroma finishing on textile substrate:

Although there are many effective approaches to micro-encapsulation⁽²³⁾ for de-creasing fragrance-release, cyclodextrins are the best regarding safety to the human body, because β -cyclodextrin has no skin irritation, no skin sensibilisation and no mutagenic effect. Detailed studies of toxicology⁽⁵⁾, mutagegicity, teratogenity and carcinogenity were indicated that the cyclodextrin can effect the human organism only at extremely high concentrations. According to OECD (Organization for economic co-operation and development) test, these cyclodextrin derivatives have no irritating or sensitivation effects and it was also proved by the clinical test of T-shirt. Cyclodextrins^(24, 25) are cyclic oligosacchraides containing six, seven eight, nine ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with a hydrophilic hydroxyl group on their outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity in the center.

⁽²⁵⁾Md. Anowar Hossain studied that Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing.

⁽²⁶⁾AK Samanta and Anowar Hossain studied that Fragrance intensity with beta cyclodextrin after different duration of normal stoppage and also after nos. of wash cycles was tested by gas chromatography and the fragrance intensity of Jasminewas found to be 15.88% after five repeat washing and the fragrance intensity wasretained 39.5% in the cotton fabric up to 100 days of normal storing without washing.⁽²⁷⁾Cyclodextrins shows greater feasibility in connection with sustainable textile finishing. Cyclodextrins are cyclic oligosaccharides with hydrophilic outer surface and a lipophilic central cavity. ⁽²⁸⁾Chitin and chitosan as multifunctional materials for surface modification

of textiles in order to enhance the properties has risen significantly. The most important applications of chitosan in textile finishing include antimicrobial, antiodor, blood coagulant, antistatic, and crease-resistant finishing which provide the potential usage in various fields.

Conclusion: Microencapsulation technique and cyclodextrin for the production of cosmetic textiles is to explore the application of cyclodextrin for the purpose of incorporating fragrance oil into cotton fabrics which will create film forming ability. 100% cotton is predominant fibre used for underwear and socks producing textiles where fragrance finishing has a great value. In literature review, the use of beta cyclodextrin as a binder for the application of microencapsulated fragrance oil results in high fragrance retention in 100% cotton fabrics. Therefore, beta cyclodextrin with microencapsulated fragrance oil can be utilised to develop textiles to achieve the necessary anti-odor finishing. Since 1980, when Szejtli first patented the bonding of CDs onto textile fibres, a lot of research has gone into the application of CDs on to textile substrates. But there is still a gap between original high level basic science and commercial applications of CDs in all industrial sectors.

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International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations
Lygten 4C, 2400, København NV, Denmark
Phone and Fax: +45 78 76 60 50

Hide original message

On 2019-06-23 11:03, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Dear Sir,

Please send me the online bank transfer details for accepted paper entitled: "Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article"

Your manuscript ID: **88919-02**

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Monday, June 10, 2019, 08:54:14 PM GMT+6, Editor, IJSEI <editor@ijsei.com> wrote:

Dear Author

Herewith we want to inform you that your paper entitled: "Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article" has been recommended for publication by Peer reviewers and Editorial Board Members without revision.

Your manuscript ID: **88919-02**

Please quote the above manuscript ID in all correspondence with us.
Your research paper will be appearing in IJSEI Vol. 8, Issue 89, June 2019 after payment verification and you will receive an official acceptance.

Kindly send back the scanned copy of the manuscript handling charges pay for sum of **55 € Euro**:

Details:

Paper handling charge: 55.00 € Euro

Additional page charge(5 € Euro per page): 0.00 € Euro

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Please pay by:

» PayPal (55 € Euro):

PayPal Account: us.mobilegsm@gmail.com (Please do not send email to this address and leave the NOTE section blank)

or

» Western Union (65 € Euro - Please note that payout amount in this method should have additional 10 € for value-added tax):

Receiver First Name: Payam

Receiver Last Name: Rezaei Moghaddam
Country: Turkey
City: Van

Find a Western Union agent in your city: <http://locations.westernunion.com>

Note that anyone can send on behalf of you.
Please send back the proof of payment (scanned) as soon as possible.

Regards
IJSEI

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Coordinator, IJSEI <editor@ijsei.com>

To: Anowar Hossain

Mon, Jun 24, 2019 at 6:21 PM

Dear Author

Thank you for your email.

According to the last email, for authors who can pay their charges via PayPal method, we can receive payments here. But because of cross-border money transfer law in Denmark, for payments less than 100€ Euro and not paying via PayPal, we collect the charges in our accounts in other countries and send them together via the banking system. For the Middle East and Asia, we collect the charges in Turkey.

Also please note that there is no limitation for authors.

Should you need any further assistance, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Sincerely Yours

Coordinator, IJSEI

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On 2019-06-23 18:54, Anowar Hossain wrote:

Dear Sir,

Thanks for your guideline, but I am confused regarding the country name turkey instead of Denmark in Western Union transfer.

Is there any limitation of author number in the paper?

Please confirm

Thanks

Md. Anowar Hossain

On Sunday, June 23, 2019, 10:17:18 PM GMT+6, Coordinator, IJSEI <editor@ijsei.com> wrote:

Dear Author

Thank you for your reply.

Following your request, herewith we want to inform you that according to cross-border money transfer law in Denmark, the minimum acceptable amount for transferring via banking system is 100€ EUR. So we have to request using mentioned methods in the acceptance email.

Should you need any further assistance, we are here to help.

Sincerely Yours

Coordinator, IJSEI

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